

D6.7

Report on pre-operational tree status

Date: 21.04.2025

Version: 1.2

**Funded by
the European Union**

SOIL O-LIVE (Grant Agreement ID: 101091255) is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EIC. Neither the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Deliverable 6.7 Report on pre-operational tree status

Document Information

Project title	SOIL BIODIVERSITY AND FUNCTIONALITY OF MEDITERRANEAN OLIVE GROVES
Project acronym	SOIL O-LIVE
Grant Agreement	101091255
Work package	WP6 – Ecosystem Services
Deliverable number and title	Deliverable 6.7 Report on pre-operational tree status.
Deliverable description	A technical report on preoperational tree status during fruit ripening. (T.6.4)
Deliverable type	R – Document, report
Dissemination level	PU – Public
Lead beneficiary	UJA
Due submission date	30 June 2024 (M18)
Submission date	28.04.2025

Document Author(s) and Reviewer(s)

Name	Entity	Role (author, reviewer)
Víctor Valenzuela-Polo	UJA	Author
Antonio J. Manzaneda	UJA	Reviewer
Ivan Sanchez Castro	UJA	Reviewer

Document history

Version	Date	Made by	Short Description of Changes
1.1	15/04/2025	Víctor Valenzuela-Polo	Draft version 1
1.2	21/04/2025	Víctor Valenzuela-Polo	Draft version 1 after internal revision

Table of Contents

Document Information.....	2
Table of contents	3
Executive Summary	4
1. Introduction	5
2. Materials and methods	5
2.1. Sample collection.....	5
2.2. Variable analyses	5
3. Results	6
3.1. Multivariate Analysis	6
3.2. Macronutrients	7
3.3. Micronutrients	9
3.3.1. Principal component analysis of micronutrients	9
3.3.2. Copper	10
4. Conclusions	12
List of figures.....	
Figure 1 - Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of all analysed elements	6
Figure 2 - Distribution of samples in PCA differentiating by management.....	6
Figure 3 - Macronutrient boxplot graphs differentiating by country	7
Figure 4 - Macronutrient boxplot graphs differentiating by management.....	8
Figure 5 - Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of micronutrients.	9
Figure 6 - Linear Model Coefficients: Influence of Nutrients on Leaf Copper Concentration	10
Figure 7 - Boxplot of Copper concentration in leaves	11

Executive summary

This report presents the initial nutritional assessment of Mediterranean olive groves conducted during the pre-operational phase of the SOIL O-LIVE project, which investigates how agricultural management practices influence the nutritional status of olive trees. The study involved the collection and analysis of 193 leaf samples from orchards in Spain, Portugal, Morocco, Italy, and Greece, representing a variety of cultivation systems including Traditional, High Density, and Organic. The samples were collected just before the 2023 olive harvest, aiming to evaluate nutrient levels at a key stage of the production cycle.

Using standard laboratory techniques, researchers assessed macro- and micronutrient concentrations in the olive leaves, applying principal component analysis (PCA) to explore relationships among nutrient levels, countries, and management systems. The findings revealed a consistent trend across countries, with Moroccan farms showing the highest macronutrient concentrations and Spanish farms exhibiting the lowest levels in nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium. Although nutrient levels across different management systems showed less variation, traditional and organic farms generally maintained adequate macronutrient levels, while high-density orchards frequently fell below recommended thresholds.

In terms of micronutrients, the analysis identified distinct patterns, with Boron associated with one principal component and metallic elements such as Zinc, Iron, and Copper linked to another. Spanish orchards and those under intensive management, displayed notably high levels of Copper and Iron. Further investigation suggested that Copper, commonly applied as a fungicide via foliar treatment, might not only be absorbed by the leaves but also remain on their surface despite pre-washing. An evident negative correlation between Copper and Potassium levels was observed, especially in Spain and Portugal, where simultaneous foliar applications of both limited potassium assimilation, potentially affecting tree health and yield.

Overall, the results underscore the impact of both regional and management-related factors on olive tree nutrition. The observed deficiencies in super-intensive systems, especially in Spain, may reflect either lower fertilization rates or the influence of precision agriculture practices. Additionally, the interaction between Copper and Potassium suggests the need for a more precise design of foliar treatment protocol to avoid negative effects. These insights are critical for optimizing fertilization practices and improving the sustainability and productivity of Mediterranean olive groves.

1. Introduction

Soil parameters such as nutrient availability, water content, and other physical and chemical properties play a crucial role in determining the nutritional status of olive trees. Agricultural practices aim to optimize these plant-related factors in order to enhance production. Moreover, management systems can significantly influence soil health, which in turn affects the nutritional condition of olive trees and ultimately their yield.

This deliverable represents the first nutritional assessment of Mediterranean olive groves during the pre-operational phase of Soil O-Live project.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Sample collection

A total of 193 samples have been analysed. The sampled orchards correspond with different types of crops: Traditional (TD), High Density (HD) and Organic (ORG), from the following countries: Spain, Portugal, Morocco, Italy and Greece.

- Spain - 80 from 16 orchards.
- Greece - 50 from 10 orchards.
- Portugal - 15 from 3 orchards.
- Italy - 40 from 8 orchards.
- Morocco – 7 from 7 orchards.

Leaf samples were collected in September 2023, before the olive harvest began, to determine the plant's nutritional status prior to harvesting. Five olive trees were selected in relation to the LUCAS point of the soil analyses, each representing a sample composed of leaves from the entire olive tree. The leaves had to be at eye level for the collector, and the 3-4 pairs of leaves collected were to exclude the first two pairs.

2.2. Variables analyses

The tree status analysis (macro- and micronutrients) of olive leaves was conducted using various standard analytical techniques. Nitrogen (N) content was determined by the Kjeldahl method, which involves the digestion of the sample with concentrated sulfuric acid to convert organic nitrogen into ammonium, followed by distillation and titration to quantify the total nitrogen. Phosphorus (P) and Boron (B) were analysed using UV/VIS spectrophotometry; after an acid digestion of the sample, specific colorimetric reactions were performed, and the absorbance was measured at characteristic wavelengths to calculate the concentrations based on calibration curves. Potassium (K), Calcium (Ca), Magnesium (Mg), Iron (Fe), Manganese (Mn), Copper (Cu), and Zinc (Zn) were quantified by flame atomic absorption spectrometry (AA-flame), where the digested samples were aspirated into a flame, and the absorption of light at element-specific wavelengths was measured, allowing for precise determination of each element's concentration.

3. Results

3.1. Multivariate analysis

Fig 1. On the left, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of all analysed elements. On the right, the contribution of each variable to the PCA dimension.

The multivariate analysis, specifically the principal component analysis (PCA), indicates that the macronutrients associated with Dimension 1 account for a significant proportion of the total data variability. In contrast, Dimension 2 primarily reflects the distribution of cations within the leaf tissue.

Fig 2. On the left, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of all analysed elements. On the right, the distribution of samples differentiating by management. The principal point represents the median of each management type and the ellipse is the standard error.

When representing the different management systems, we observe a clear differentiation on the left side of the plot, where intensified farms are further from areas with high macronutrient concentrations.

3.2. Macronutrients

Fig 3. Macronutrient boxplot graphs differentiating by country.

The trend at the country level is similar for all macronutrients (nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium), with a significant relationship between the element and the "Country" category in each case. Regarding the highest levels, the trend places Moroccan farms above all others,

remaining within the reference levels for both deficiency and toxicity in leaves, with similar trends in other countries, except Spain. In Spanish farms, a deficiency is observed for all macronutrients.

Fig 4. Macronutrient boxplot graphs differentiating by country.

When representing by management type, this differentiation loses significance, but clear and similar trends are observed across all nutrients. The medians for traditional and organic

management fall within the reference parameters, with traditional farms showing higher concentrations of macronutrients in the leaves. In contrast, intensified orchards present the lowest levels, even falling below the deficiency threshold for some elements.

3.3. Micronutrients

3.3.1. Principal component analysis of micronutrients

Fig 5. Top left, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of micronutrients. Top right, the contribution of each variable to the PCA dimension. Bottom, the distribution of samples differentiating by country.

The multivariate analysis reveals two dimensions that explain the variance in olive leaf composition. On one hand, Dimension 1 is associated with the concentration of Boron, while Dimension 2 is linked to metallic elements such as Zinc, Iron, and Copper. A significant differentiation is observed in Spanish orchards, where higher concentrations of Copper and Iron are found.

3.3.2. Copper

The concentration of copper in the soil was previously analysed in D2.1, and it is necessary to assess the interaction of this element with other nutrients, as it is applied as a fungicide in olive trees via foliar application.

Fig 6. Linear Model Coefficients: Influence of Nutrients on Leaf Copper Concentration.

We primarily found a positive and significant relationship with micronutrients, such as Boron and Zinc. On the other hand, a significant negative relationship was observed with Manganese and Potassium.

Fig 7. Boxplot of Copper concentration in leaves differentiating by country (top) and by management (bottom).

The levels of copper found in the leaves suggest that we might be observing not only the copper absorbed by the leaf but also the copper adsorbed on its surface. The leaf pre-processing involves washing with neutral soap, but this may not be sufficient to remove copper from the surface.

The differences found by country and management type highlight a notable change in the trend for Spain and high-intensity orchards. Potassium concentrations in these orchards were very low, while a similar trend was observed for copper, but in the opposite direction.

This could be of importance, as in Spain and some farms in Portugal (HD management), foliar potassium applications are accompanied by copper treatments. This could suggest a potassium exclusion (also from foliar incorporation) due to the simultaneous application of copper in the treatment.

4. Conclusions

Spanish orchards and super-intensive farms show lower levels of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium compared to the rest. This could be related either to the production levels during the year or to the fertilization rates applied. In the case of super-intensive farms, the lower nutrient levels might also reflect the use of precision agriculture practices, where only the necessary amounts are supplied.

Additionally, copper shows a negative relationship with potassium. Particularly in Spain and Portugal, potassium levels are low, which may be due to copper's interference with potassium uptake when both elements are applied simultaneously through foliar treatments.